

Sanjiejiao (三階教)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Language, Sino-Tibetan, Sinitic

Sanjiejiao (三階教), or Pufa-zong (普法宗), the Three-Stages Movement, is a Buddhist Sect founded by the Zen master Xinxing (信行, 540-594) in the Sui-Dynasty China, banned by the Tang Dynasty, and gradually disappeared then. Sanjiejiao is mainly based on the pufa" (普法, universal dharma)" doctrine while its main classics, Sanjie Jilu (三階集錄, Sanjie Collection) and Sanjie Fofa (三階佛法, Sanjie Buddhism), were compiled based on the Huayan Classics and others. All were lost after the Tang Dynasty, while the complete Sanjiejiao documents were discovered in Jinchuanwan Village (Chunhua, Shaanxi) in 1981. Some classics were introduced to Japan in the early Tang period, inspiring Japanese adherents to continue the school afterwards. Sanjiejiao's philosophy bases on the Buddhist Sad-dharma Puṇḍarīka Sūtra, or the Fahua Sūtra (法華經/The Lotus Sūtra), divides the evolution of the universe into the True Dharma (正法, Zhengfa; Sad-dharma), The Likely Dharma (像法, Xiangfa; Sad-dharma-pratirūpaka), and the Declining Dharma (末法, Mofa; Sad-dharma-vipralopa). Sanjiejiao aims at asceticism and humiliation, advocating that everyone has his own "dharma" in his heart-mind, so he can practice "dharma" to achieve a transcendence. Sanjiejiao advocates the concept of Tri-kāla (佛法三時, Three Stages of Buddhism), divides Dharma into three categories based on time, place, and people, and each category, in turn, is divided into three phases (sanjie). The three phases of time include the True Dharma lasting for 500 years (after Buddha's death), the Likely Dharma lasting for 1000 years, and the Declining Dharma lasting for 10,000 years. The place is divided into the Land of Purity (淨土, Jingtū), the land of the dirty (穢土, Huitū), and the secular world. Sanghas are divided into the Wise Monks (智慧僧眾, zhihui sengzhong) and the Mute Sheep Monks (瘖羊僧, yayang seng). Due to the limitation in capacity, the Mute Sheep Monks should practice "formless samādhi" (無相三昧, wuxiang sanmei) to achieve the goals. Sentiment beings are divided into three levels based on their moral roots: the "bodhisattvas" who have the ability for the One Vehicle [the Ekayāna]; the ones have the ability for the Three Vehicles [that of the śravaka, the pratyekabuddha, and the bodhisattva] and practiced "formless samādhi" in their previous lives; and those who break the precepts and the views, thus residing in communities to practice the pufa doctrine. Sanjiejiao highlights the role of the "never despise" Sadāparibhūta Bodhisattva and advocates reciting Ksitigarbha Bodhisattva, instead of Shakyamuni Buddha. Sanjiejiao focuses on the pufa doctrine, all sentiment beings have "Buddha-nature" and deserve to get "universal veneration" (普敬, pujing).

Date Range: 500 CE - 800 CE

Region: Shaanxi

Region tags: China, Shaanxi Province 陕西省

The central land of Tang Dynasty China

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Hubbard, Jamie. 1991. "Chinese Reliquary Inscriptions and the San-chieh-chiao." *Journal of the*

International Association of Buddhist Studies 14: 253-280.

- Source 2: Ishii, Kosei 石井公成. 2017. "Huayan and Chan in the Context of East Asian Buddhism." *International Journal of Buddhist Thought & Culture* 27(1): 161-192.
- Source 3: Jan, Yun-hua 冉雲華. 1983. 'Dunhuang wenxian yu Sengchou de chanfa' 敦煌文獻與僧稠的禪法 [Dunhuang Documents and the Chan Teachings of Sengchou]. In *Hua-Kang Buddhist Journal* 華崗佛學學報 06: 73-103. Online version: https://www.chibs.edu.tw/ch_html/hkbj/06/hkbj0604.htm.
- Source 1: Nishimoto Teruma 西本照真. 1998. *Sankaikyō no kenkyū* 三階教の研究 (Studies on the Teaching of the Three Stages). Tokyo: Shunjū-sha.
- Source 2: Nishimoto Teruma 西本照真. 1978. "Sankai kyōto no hanbetsu kijun -- mi shōkai sekkoku shiryō o chūshin to shite (三階教徒の判別規準 -- 未紹介石刻資料を中心として, Criteria for identifying Sanjiejiao believers - Focusing on un-introduced stone carving materials.) 印度學佛教學研究 (Indian studies and Buddhist studies) 46(2): 181-5.
- Source 1: Zhang Zong 張總. 2013. *Zhongguo Sanjiejiao shi: yi ge fo jiao shi shang yan mie de jiao pai* (中國三階教史: 一個佛教史上湮滅的教派, The History of China's Sanjiejiao: An Annihilated Sect in the History of Buddhism.) Beijing: China National Philosophy and Social Sciences Achievement Library 國家哲學社會科學成果文庫.
- Source 2: Tsukamoto Zenryū 塚本善隆. 1937. "Sangaikyō shiryō zakki (三階教資料雜記, Sankei teaching Miscellaneous records of Sanjiejiao)." *Shina bukkyō shigaku* 1: 57-74
- Source 3: Yabuki, Keiki 矢吹慶輝. 1927. *Sangai-kyō no kenkyū* (三階教の研究, Study on Sanjiejiao). Tokyo: Iwanami
- Source 1: Yang Xueyong 楊學勇. 2014. "Sanjiejiao shi yanjiu de jige wenti (三階教史研究的幾個問題, Several issues in the study of the Sanjiejiao history)." *Dunhuang Academic Journal* 敦煌學輯刊 2 (2): 143-155
- Source 2: Yang Xueyong 楊學勇. 2016. "Sanjiejiao yu Jingtujiao de lunzheng - weirao zhe "buhe dusong dacheng jingdian" kanzhan (三階教與淨土教的論爭 - 圍繞著「不合讀誦大乘經典」展開, The debate between the Sanjiejiao and the Pure Land Sect - revolves around "incompatible reading and recitation of Mahayana classics)." *Chinese Buddhism* 中國佛學 2: 106-116.
- Source 3: Yang Xueyong 楊學勇. 2017. *Sanjiejiao shi yanjiu* (三階教史研究, Study on Sanjiejiao History). Dunhuang and Silk Road Research Series 敦煌與絲路研究叢書. Lanzhou: Gansu wen hua chu ban she
- Source 1: Greene, Eric. 2008. 'Another Look at Early Chan: Daoxuan, Bodhidharma, and the Three Levels Movement'. *T'oung Pao* 94(1-3): 49-114
- Source 2: Lin, Pei-ying. 2020. "Repositioning Xinxing 信行 (540-594) in the Chinese Meditation Tradition: Xinxing's Teaching on the Formless Samādhi." *Journal of Chan Buddhism* 1: 55-76
- Source 3: Bai Wen 白文. 2011. "Sanjiejiao xinyang yu Chunhua Jinwanchuan shique yishu (三階教信仰與淳化金川灣石窟藝術, The Sanjiejiao Beliefs and the Art of the Jinchuan Bay Grottoes in Chunhua)." *World of cultural relics* 文物世界 1: 40-45.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Hubbard Jamie. The Manuscript Remains and Other Materials for the Study of the Sanchieh Movement. Smith College. <https://sophia.smith.edu/~jhubbard/publications/books/materials/>.
- Source 1 Description: The Manuscript Remains and Other Materials related to Sanjiejiao are presented in english, valuable for the study of Sanjiejiao worldwide.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: Li Jianchao (李健超). “Chang'an Sanjiejiao Temple and Zhongnan Mountain Sanjiejiao Holy Land (長安三階寺院與終南山三階教聖地).” Silk Road Multimedia Series Resource Library: Cultural Relics and Monuments (絲路多媒體系列資源庫：文物古蹟篇), https://www.sxlib.org.cn/dfzy/sczl/wwgjp/yj/201808/t20180806_928603.html.
- Source 1 Description: Stone stelea Inscriptions in major Sanjiejiao temples in Shaanxi are presented and discussed (with images/photos attached).

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao is closely related to Zen Buddhism, but has a contradictory relationship with Pure Land Buddhism and others. There are similarities between Sanjiejiao and Tang Zen Buddhism, both absorbing some important parts from the perspective of Huayan philosophy (see Kosei Ishii 2017, 186). Master Xinxing indeed attached great importance to seated meditation (坐禪, zuochan). The Dunhuang manuscript known as Zhifa (制法) wrote that “seated meditation alone should be considered the fundamental practice for all the evil monks of the evil world after the Buddha’s extinction” (惡世界佛滅度後，一切惡出家人唯以坐禪為). These concepts of Sanjiejiao were described as contradicting the theories and practices of other Buddhist sects (such as Tiantai-zong, Huayan-zong, Pure Land Buddhism, and even Chan Buddhism) in China at that time. The Sanjiejiao were accused of rejecting monastic discipline, erasing distinctions between lay and clergy, and denying the utility of the traditional canonical corpus (see Greene 2008, 82; Yang Xueyong 2016, 111-4; Lin 2020, 56).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao was noticed and rejected by monks and adherents of many other Buddhist sects. Sanjiejiao adepts and followers believed that all Buddha statues were earthen figures and did not need respect; instead, sentiment beings with Buddha nature should be respected.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Together with the Tang Dynasty Central Government, monks and adherents of other Buddhist sects attacked Sanjiejiao many times during the early 8th centuries (ie., in 600, 695, 699, and 725) which led to the fall of this school at the the post-Tang Dynasty periods.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao disciples must be approved to stay, study and practice dharma in separate Sanjiejiao temples. Adherents were requested to follow specific Sanjiejiao principles.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: The adepts of Sanjiejiao were almost all men, while its followers were both males and females. Some Japanese records such as Zhenyuan Shijiaolu (貞元釋教錄, Records of Zhenyuan Buddhism) show that monks and nuns lived in various Sanjiejiao temples in Chang'an City, the capital of the Tang Dynasty.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao set up their own ritual structures; disciples and adherents must have participated in.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: The practice of one meal a day and always begging for food; the practice of pufa (universal dharma) and pujing (universal veneration)

Notes: Sanjiejiao advocated that monks should live separately from the rest of clergy, practice dhūta (頭陀, austerity) of eating only one meal a day and always beg for food (see Greene 2008, 93, 96). While walking on the road, Sanjiejiao monks and believers must bow to everyone they see because according to their Buddhist teachings, this is a sign of trust and enlightenment in the Buddha nature of all passers-by.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sanjiejiao texts do not clearly mention this point.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Tang Dynasty Central Government declared Sanjiejiao as a heterodox sect, thus (Sanjiejiao) was attacked several times in the early 8th century and finally disappeared.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: General numbers of adepts and adherents were not known; however, according to Pei Xuanzheng (裴玄証)'s work, Xinxing chanshi mingtabei (信行禪師銘塔碑, Monument of Zen Master Xinxing), Master Xinxing had more than 300 prominent disciples, among whom the most influential ones are Hui Si 慧思 (515-577), Seng Yong (僧邕, 543-631), Ben Ji (本濟, 562-615), Hui Liao (慧了, ? ~656), Shan Zhi (善智, ?~?), Pei Xuanzheng (裴玄証, ?~?), Hui Ru (慧如, ? ~618), Gao Jiong (高顛, ? ~607), and so on.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Field doesn't know

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Two main Sanjiejiao classics (written by Master Xinxing) include Sanjie Jilu (三階集錄, Sanjie Collection) and Sanjie Fofa (三階佛法, Sanjie Buddhism). Both were specially adapted and compiled based on previous Buddhist scriptures from other sects, especially the Huayan School Classics.

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Master Xinxing's works, Sanjie Jilu (三階集錄, Sanjie Collection) and Sanjie Fofa (三階佛法, Sanjie Buddhism), were lost after the Tang Dynasty periods; only parts of them were included in the writings of disciples of later generations as well as in the writings of monks of other sects.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: After the discoveries in Dunhuang and Jinchuanwan Village in the 1970s-1980s, scholars of various disciplines read and interpreted Sanjiejiao main classics for the sake of academic research and public introduction.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The modern scholars read, interpret, and introduce the Sanjiejiao scriptures to the whole world.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: According to Zhenyuan Shijiaolu (貞元釋教錄, Records of Zhenyuan Buddhism) circulated in Japan, in the early ninth century AD, there were many Sanjie temples in Chang'an (the capital of Tang China) with more than a thousand monks and nuns practicing its rituals. However, during the post-Tang periods, all Sanjiejiao temples were occupied by other Buddhist sects or collapsed.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao symbol: the Buddhist Dharma Vehicle Wheel.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Sanjiejiao belief, those who practiced wuxingsanmei rituals (for the second category of sentiment beings) and the pufa doctrine (for the third category of sentiment beings) could get transcended.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners and followers of the Sanjiejiao believed that once death or transcendence occurs, only the soul continues its journey to the Buddha's world or reincarnation.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The body is a temporary existence, and only the soul (toward transcendence/reincarnation) is eternal.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanjiejiao adepts and followers believed in samsara and wished to access to nirvana or to get reincarnated.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: nirvana

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: nirvana

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Sanjiejiao belief, practitioners and believers can enter the Buddha's kingdom (Nirvana) or be reincarnated based on their merits and cultivation achievements.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiaojie adepts and believers practiced collective forest burial. This practice is seen as most significant act of alms in the sect's philosophy. The Sanjiejiao adepts sacrificed the body to the wild beasts, collected the bones and placed them in a tower in the temple's backyard. The bones of Master Xinxing himself after his death were collected in this burial method and placed in a temple's burial tower at the Mingbu valley (also known as Zigu) in Zhongnan Mountain. According to some records, for example, *Jinshi Xubian* (金石续篇), *Taozhaizang shiji* (陶斋藏石记), and *Baqiongshi jinshi buzheng* (八琼室金石补正), Master Xin Xing's disciples during the late Sui and early Tang Dynasties such as Ben Ji (本济), Hui Zi (慧了), Seng Hai (僧海), Shang Zhi (尚直), Dao An (道安), Guan Zhen (管真), Pei Xuanzheng (裴玄証), Guan Jun (管均), and others continued this burial method. By the middle of the Tang Dynasty, more and more Sanjiejiao tomb towers were built. The Sanjiejiao believers were different. From the beginning of the eighth century they began to practice cremation.

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Adepts and followers of later periods of Sanjiejiao history practiced cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: During the beginning period, Sanjiejiao adepts and some adherents practiced forest burials to serve the beasts.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Bones left from forest burials were collected and reburied in the temple stupas.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Bones of Master Xinxing, Sanjiejiao adepts (and adherents?) collected after the collective forest burials were buried in stupa(s) built inside the temple space.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: collective stupa inside a temple space

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary followers could choose to bury the deceased in their own cemetery or cremate.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Family burial or cremation

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: As the embodiment of the doctrine of “never despise”, Sanjiejiao highlights the role of Sadāparibhūta Bodhisattva, a Bodhisattva who never looks down on others and does respectful things. According to the Fahua Sūtra, Sadāparibhūta Bodhisattva is the previous life of Shakyamuni Buddha. In addition, the Sanjiejiao advocates reciting Ksitigarbha Bodhisattva, which is different from the Pure Land Sect which relies on reciting the name of Sakyamuni Buddha

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: All Buddhas in Sanjiejiao's belief are anthropomorphic.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: All Buddhas live in a Buddha land that is higher than and away from the profane world.

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Sanjiejiao followers worshipped many buddhas, among which Dizang pusa (地藏菩薩, Kṣitigarbha) is the Bodhisattva who take care of the deceased souls.

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Buddha rewards those who uphold the Dharma (transcendence or reincarnation). Those who live virtuous lives are also guided "through the sea of suffering."

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No
Notes: There are not enough clues to confirm that the Buddha in the Sanjiejiao has negative emotions or sets punishments for humans.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes
Notes: Sanjiejiao is undoubtedly a polytheistic sect.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– No
Notes: The Buddhas in the Sanjiejiao only communicate with humans indirectly through the moral principles of cause and effect.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Although popular Buddhist beliefs acknowledge the existence of deceased ancestral spirits (such as the story of monk Mu Qianlian rescuing the mother spirit from hell); the classics and texts related to Sanjiejiao do not explicitly mention it.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: They "appeared" in dreams or being told by religious specialists.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Believers could only "feel" by their heart-mind.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The divines have the ability to know and govern the secular world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They have the ability to know all aspects of the secular world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The divines' knowledge and rules have no boundaries.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: There is no boundaries in their knowledge.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the non-human divines in Sanjiejiao come from other religions, such as Daoism and folk religions, and therefore their knowledge is thought to be unlimited to one region or within Sanjiejiao Sect.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: They can see people anywhere

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: There is no limitation.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The divines can evaluate the merits/virtues of people through their heart-mind.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The divines have the power to handle the inner nature of human beings

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The divines were told to see people's past and future through the laws of cause and effect.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The divines have the ability to possess endless/infinite knowledge about the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: They evaluate the dharma of each person and reward him/her accordingly

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are not enough clues to confirm, but according to the law of cause and effect, the divines perform the task of punishing those who violate the

precepts in order to protect the dharma.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Followers acknowledge the power of these divines by believing in the law of cause and effect.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: As the protectors of Dharma, the divines are believed to have positive emotion towards those who keep the precepts and good views.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: There are no clear clues confirming the presence of negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

- Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao adepts believed that they could get transcended after death.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanjiejiao believed that a thousand years after the birth of the Buddha, there are still many

sages/saints who hold good precepts and have correct views. They can guide sentient beings through biefafa method (corresponding to the first stage (zhengfa period) and second stages (xiangfa period) of Buddhism). Entering the third stage (mofa, the age of Ending Dharma), people break the precepts with empty views must rely on the pufafa method.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Sanjiejiao dharma concept, all living beings are essentially Tathagatagarbha and can “transform” to be Buddhas, hence Buddha has no real name. This is why Buddha is called “nameless” (無名, wuming). Buddha has no reality, so it is called “formless” (無相, wuxiang). Tathagatagarbha Buddha will restore the universe after 11,500 years after the death of Shakyamuni Buddha (after the Ending Dharma period).

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Tathagatagarbha Buddhas will appear during a lifetime, but the Great Messiah Movement will appear 11,500 years after the death of Shakyamuni Buddha (according to the three-stage teaching).

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: In the Sanjie belief, in every period, there are always Buddhas present to protect the Dharma and guide all living beings to practice the pufafa doctrine

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: All good living beings are essentially Tathagatagarbha and can “transform” to be

Buddhas to protect the dharma.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Tathagatagarbha Buddhas is responsible for protecting the dharma and promote/restore the Sanjiejiao tradition.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: protecting the dharma, ensuring the law of cause and effect, honoring the Sanbao (Buddha, dharma, and sanghas).

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao divides the evolution of the universe and human world into three main stages, ie., the True Dharma (正法, Zhengfa; Sad-dharma), The Likely Dharma (像法, Xiangfa; Sad-dharma-pratirūpaka), and the Declining Dharma (末法, Mofa; Sad-dharma-vipralopa).

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - No
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
 - Notes: The new circle will come after 11,500 years after the death of Shakyamuni Buddha.
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao advocated the doctrine of pufa (普法, universal dharma). The pufa doctrine does not distinguish between dharma traditions, between people of all classes, immortals and mortals; instead, all sentient beings have "Buddha-nature" and deserve to get "universal veneration" (普敬, pujing). The doctrine of universal veneration is corresponding to the aforementioned concept of "never despise" (不輕, buqing) in Xin Xing's ideology. The pufa dharma is also called "blind" dharma (盲法, mangfa), which refers to a person who is blind from birth and does not need/unable to distinguish colors. In order to perform the pufa dharma thoroughly, the Sanjiejiao established the concept of biefa (别法) to divide people into two categories: those with high and low merits in practicing dharma (or those who uphold or break the precepts and good views). The Sanjiejiao believed that a thousand years after the birth of the Buddha, there are still many sages/saints who hold good precepts and have correct views. They can guide sentient beings through biefa method (corresponding to the first stage (zhengfa period) and second stages (xiangfa period) of Buddhism). Entering the third stage (mofa, the age of Ending Dharma), people break the precepts with empty views must rely on the pufa method.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao focused on the Pufa doctrine; therefore, they highlighted the practice of puji among the commoners

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao masters and monks required celibacy, lived and practiced dharma in separate

temples. Ordinary followers do not need to perform celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy was strictly applied to masters and monks, but not to popular followers (sentiment beings).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao adepts ate one meal a day only (vegetarian food only). Regular followers eat vegetarian food on certain days or throughout the year (but not required)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao adepts practiced vegetarianism.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Believers went to Sanjiejiao temples to make offerings to Buddha on special religious days (but not required).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Adepts and followers gathered to held/participate in regular rituals at local temples

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Monks who wished to become ordained must have attended strictly supervised Buddhist training courses offered by Sanjiejiao temples. He/she must have met the requirements to be recognized as a Sanjiejiao master/monk(nun).

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Sanjiejiao monks and nuns advocated living closely with believers (community).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Group rituals were held regularly every day at Sanjiejiao temples.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao adepts and followers gathered at the Sanjiejiao to participate in special collective rituals dedicated to Buddhas and the Dharma.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Generally, in the rituals of Buddhist temples, there is always guidance and observation.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes
Notes: Synchronic practices were required in collective rituals

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The dharma wheel, Sanjiejiao flag(s), Sanjiejiao clothing (unclear).

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– Yes

Notes: Non-violence, non-killing, non-dharma violation.

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and nuns practiced vegetarianism, ordinary followers were not required.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and nuns must have taken hair cutting while ordinary followers were not required.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and nuns were required to wear Sanjiejiao attire, and ordinary believers were also required to wear specific religious attire when attending ceremonies in Sanjiejiao temples.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: In rituals, both Chinese and Pali/Sanskrit were probably used.

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Sanjiejiao takes alms and philanthropy very seriously. Generally, an inexhaustible storehouse (無盡藏, wújìncáng) will be set up in the temple yard to perform the service. According to a record from the Huadu Temple in Chang'an during the Tang Dynasty, wujincang was a useful charity center that not only provided food, clothing, but also farming facilities (see Wei Shu (韋述) in Huadu Temple's Wujincang (化度寺無盡藏院)). Sanjiejiao temples in Hebei, Henan, Gansu, Sichuan and other places have also opened similar wujincang.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The Sanjiejiao adepts and followers organized the relief works themselves.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, from the perspective that almost all Sanjiejiao temples officially established Wuzangjin for poverty alleviation.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Adepts needed to be trained in the initial stage, and modification courses were held regularly; ordinary believers were not required but they could participate in public teaching courses held at Sanjiejiao temples.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanjiejiao was once a well-organized system with a strict hierarchy and task structure among practitioners. Every monk or nun must have acknowledged his or her own position.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Followers lived a secular life in accordance with the laws and responsibilities regulated by the state.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: The inexhaustible storehouses (無盡藏, wújìncáng) were set up in the Sanjiejiao temple yard to perform the alms and philanthropy services.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary followers were applied taxes and other duties regulated by the imperial states

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Both adepts and ordinary followers lived under the state law. Local authorities provided security protection.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: All experts and casual followers were governed by state and local laws.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and nuns who violated religious regulations were subject to strict re-education or expulsion from the Sanjiejiao community

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Serious violations by monks and nuns would result in expulsion.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Serious violations by monks and nuns would result in expulsion.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: State and local authorities used state laws to enforce rule over the adepts and followers

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Under Imperial law, serious violations would result in exile

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Tang Dynasty Law

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary followers must have performed all military duties prescribed by the state. In the early 8th century AD, under the suppression of the Tang Dynasty, Sanjiejiao monks were forced to convert to the Pure Land Sect or were sent to serve in the military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Imperial law, ordinary followers were obviously subject for military service.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There is no distinct written language used in Sanjiejiao; instead, Master Xinxing and Sanjiejiao adepts used the general Han Chinese scriptures when composing classics and other religious documents.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanjiejiao adepts and followers used the Han Chinese scripture system regulated by the imperial governments.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They used standardized Chinese script, which was granted and supervised by state agents.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanjiejiao also used Buddhist calendar to arrange and perform rituals/festivals.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They used the official calendar regulated by the imperial court.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Except for ordinary believers who lived a secular life.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to the Sect's principle, Sanjiejiao monks and nuns had to beg for food from the community every day.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sanjiejiao (三階教), HONG, Jae-song. "The Influence of the Three Stages Sect (sanjiejiao)" 47, no. 2 (1999). <https://doi.org/10.4259/ibk.47.808>.

Reference: Sanjiejiao (三階教), Katō, Hirota. "Integration of Buddhist Thought in the &i&t;nianfo Sanmei Baowang Lun&i&t;/i&t; 念仏三昧宝王論: In Relation to the Anti-sanjiejiao 三階教 (three Stages Teaching) Stance of the &i&t;nianfo Jing&i&t;/i&t; 念仏鏡" 68, no. 1 (December 20, 2019). https://doi.org/10.4259/ibk.68.1_180.

Reference: Sanjiejiao (三階教), Nagao, Koe. "Attitudes in Opposition to the Sanjiejiao 三階教 in the &i&t;qunyi Lun &i&t;/i&t; 群疑論: The Discussion About Acquisition and Non-acquisition" 68, no. 2 (March 20, 2020). https://doi.org/10.4259/ibk.68.2_755.

Reference: Sanjiejiao (三階教), NISHIMOTO, Teruma. "The Concept of Jie in the Sanjiejiao (three Stages) School" 40, no. 2 (1992). <https://doi.org/10.4259/ibk.40.602>.

Reference: Sanjiejiao (三階教), SEOK, Gil-Am. "The Vajrasamadhi Sutra (金剛三昧經) and the Three Stages Sect (三階教)" 58, no. 2 (2010). https://doi.org/10.4259/ibk.58.2_1063.